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Capturing the Red Queen using Adaptive Dynamics in a
predator-prey coevolution.

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Abstract

In this paper we describe the coevolution of phenotypes in a community of predators and of prey using adaptive dynamics. Evolutionary cycling can be one of the outcome of the process. The Models on which the description is based are formed from microscopic stochastic birth and death events, together with a process of random mutation. Births and deaths, can occur as a results of phenotype-dependent interactions between predator and prey individuals and therefore natural selection can be generated . We demonstrate three outcomes of evolution in this paper. A community may evolve to a state at which the predator becomes extinct, or to one at which the species coexist with constant phenotypic values, or the species may coexist with cyclic changes in phenotypic values. The last outcome corresponds to a Red Queen dynamic, in which the selection pressures arising from the predator-prey interaction cause the species to evolve without ever reaching an equilibrium phenotypic state. The Red Queen dynamic will require an intermediate harvesting efficiency of the prey by the predator and sufficiently high evolutionary rate constant of the prey, and is complex when the model is made stochastic and phenotypically polymorphic. A cyclic outcome lies outside the contemporary focus on evolutionary equilibria, and argues for an extension to a dynamical framework for describing the asymptotic states of evolution.

Declaration

I, the undersigned, hereby declare that the work contained in this project is my original work, and that any work done by others or by myself previously has been acknowledged and referenced accordingly.

Chauke Hlupheka Evans

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1. Introduction and background

The Red Queen's Hypothesis also referred to as Red Queen, Red Queen's race or Red Queen Effect, is an evolutionary hypothesis. The term is taken from the Red Queen's race in Lewis Carroll's *Through the Looking-Glass*. The Red Queen said, "It takes all the running you can do, to keep in the same place". The Red Queen Principle can be stated thus:

In reference to an evolutionary system, continuing adaptation is needed in order for a species to maintain its relative fitness amongst the systems being co-evolved with..

The hypothesis is intended to explain two different phenomena: the advantage of sexual reproduction at the level of individuals, and the constant evolutionary arms race between competing species. In the first (micro-evolutionary) version, by making every individual an experiment when mixing mother's and father's genes, sexual reproduction may allow a species to evolve quickly just to hold onto the ecological niche that it already occupies in the ecosystem. In the second (macro-evolutionary) version, the probability of extinction for groups (usually families) of organisms is hypothesized to be constant within the group and random among groups.

(i) Evolution of sexual reproduction

Science writer Matt Ridley popularized the term "the red queen" in connection with sexual selection in his book *The Red Queen*. In the book, Ridley discussed the debate in theoretical biology over the adaptive benefit of sexual reproduction to those species in which it appears. The connection of the Red Queen to this debate arises from the fact that the traditionally accepted theory (Vicar of Bray) only showed adaptive benefit at the level of the species or group, not at the level of the gene (although, it must be added here that the protean 'Vicar of Bray' adaptation is very useful to some species that belong to the lower levels of the food chain). By contrast, a Red-Queen-type theory that organisms are running cyclic arms races with their parasites can explain the utility of sexual reproduction at the level of the gene by positing that the role of sex is to preserve genes that are currently disadvantageous, but that will become advantageous against the background of a likely future population of parasites.

Sex is an evolutionary puzzle. In most sexual species, males make up half the population, yet they bear no offspring directly and generally contribute little to the survival of offspring. In fact, in some species, such as lions, males pose a positive threat to live young fathered by other males. In addition, males and females must spend resources to attract and compete for mates. Sexual selection also can favor traits that reduce the fitness of an organism, such as brightly colored plumage in birds of paradise that

increases the likelihood for an individual to be noticed by predators and potential mates. Thus, sexual reproduction can be highly inefficient.

One possible explanation for the fact that nearly all vertebrates are sexual is that sex increases the rate at which adaptation can occur. This is for two reasons. Firstly, if an advantageous mutation occurs in an asexual line, it is impossible for that mutation to spread without wiping out all other lines, which may have different advantageous mutations of their own. Secondly, it mixes up alleles. Some instances of genetic variation might be advantageous only when paired with other mutations, and sex increases the likelihood that such pairings will occur. Also, in asexually reproducing organisms, especially parthenogenetic organisms, mutations conferring an advantageous allele will have to occur twice, before the advantageous allele becomes fixed in the population, resulting in a longer phase where the heterozygote for the disadvantageous allele (relative to the new advantageous allele) is fixed in the population.

For sex to be advantageous for these reasons requires constant selection for changing conditions. One factor that might cause this is the constant arms race between parasites and their hosts. Parasites generally evolve quickly because of their short life cycles. As they evolve, they attack their hosts in a variety of ways. Two consecutive generations might be faced with very different selective pressures. If this change is rapid enough, it might explain the persistence of sex.

(ii) Arms races

Originally proposed by Leigh Van Valen (1973), the metaphor of an evolutionary arms race has been found appropriate for the descriptions of biological processes with dynamics similar to arms races. Van Valen proposed the Red Queen's Hypothesis as an explanatory tangent to his proposed "Law of Extinction" (also 1973), which he derived from observation of constant probabilities of extinction within families of organisms across geological time. Put differently, Van Valen found that the ability of a family of organisms to survive does not improve over time, and that the probability of extinction for any given family is random. The Red Queen's Hypothesis as formulated by Van Valen provides a conceptual underpinning to discussions of evolutionary arms races, even though a direct test of the hypothesis remains elusive, particularly at the macro-evolutionary level. This concept remains similar to that of a system obeying a self-organized criticality.

For example, because every improvement in one species will lead to a selective advantage for that species, variation will normally continuously lead to increases in fitness in one species or another. However, since in general different species are co-evolving, improvement in one species implies that it will get a competitive advantage over the other species, and thus be able to capture a larger share of the resources available to all. This means that fitness increase in one evolutionary system will tend to lead to

fitness decrease in another system. The only way that a species involved in a competition for resources can maintain its fitness relative to other competing species is by improving its specific fitness (From Heylighen, 2000).

The most obvious example of this effect are the "arms races" between predators and prey (e.g. Vermeij, 1987), where the only way predators can compensate for a better defence by the prey (e.g. rabbits running faster than their parents) is by developing a better offense (e.g. foxes running faster than their parents). In this case we might consider the relative improvements (rabbits running faster than foxes or vice versa) to be also absolute improvements in fitness (From Heylighen, 2000).

An example of the Red Queen Hypothesis might be one of the plants that evolve toxins to kill off predators such as caterpillars. If the plant, under predation selection pressure, evolved a new type of toxin to which the caterpillar had no immunity, most of the caterpillars would die off and the tree would flourish. This victory would be short lived, as only the caterpillars immune to the toxin, even if only a tiny percentage would breed rapidly, and once again the tree would be under attack.

To make this notion clear, we define the Red queen dynamic as any phenotypic that, in the absence of external forces, does not tend to an equilibrium state. For the investigation of whether Red Queen dynamics are possible, Many Models for evolutionary dynamics of predator and prey phenotypes were developed (Marrow, 1992; Marrow et al, 1992; Marrow and Cannings, 1993). The Models suggests that, During evolution, the phenotypes can either tend to an equilibrium or a non-equilibrium states. The models did not take time into consideration explicitly, and for this reason could only give only qualitative information on the direction of evolution. To determine the asymptotic states of coevolving systems, it is very necessary to construct all the time-dependent processes into the framework of dynamical systems. Section 3 briefly describe the concept of adaptive dynamics in a predator-prey community, section 4 Introduces the ecological interactions which defines the predator-prey community, section 5 briefly explains the features of the model used, and in section 6 we show that the system eventually attains one of three different evolutionary outcomes : (i) the predator goes extinct, (ii) coevolution leads to a constant phenotypes in predator and prey, and (iii) the phenotypes in both species undergo coupled and sustained oscillations on a limit cycle corresponding to Red queen dynamics.

2. Aims and objectives

In this paper, we will explore the canonical equation (ODE) of adaptive dynamics and apply the approach to examine the red-queen dynamics in a predator-prey. we utilize a hierarchy of dynamical models to investigate the phenotypic states to which coevolving predators and prey could tend. These model represent different balances between descriptive capacity and corresponding analytic tractability.

3. Adaptive dynamics

The basic principle of evolution via natural selection, survival of the fittest, was outlined by the naturalist Charles Darwin in his 1859 book, *On the Origin of Species*. Darwin expressed his arguments verbally, but many attempts have since then been made to formalize the theory of evolution. The well known are population genetics which aim to model the biological basis of inheritance but usually at the expense of ecological detail, quantitative genetics which incorporates quantitative traits influenced by genes at many loci and evolutionary game theory which ignores genetic detail but incorporates a high degree of ecological realism, in particular that the success of any given strategy depends on the frequency at which strategies are played in the population, a concept known as frequency dependence.

Adaptive Dynamics is a set of techniques developed during the 1990s. They link population dynamics to evolutionary dynamics and incorporate and generalize the fundamental idea of frequency dependent selection from game theory. In other words, evolutionary invasion analysis, also known as adaptive dynamics is a mathematical theory that explicitly links population dynamics to long-term evolution driven by mutation and natural selection, as the traits vary continuously and gives rise to non-linear invasion fitness. It provides methods of model formulation, methods of model analysis and mathematical theorems that relate phenomena on an evolutionary time scale to processes and structures defined in ecological and population dynamical terms. It can be applied to various ecological settings and is particularly suitable for incorporating ecological complexity.

In the next section we introduce the fundamental ideas behind Adaptive Dynamics. Then, in Section 2.2, the theory is presented in detail for monomorphic populations. In particular, we will explain the invasion fitness, the selection gradient, Evolutionarily Singular Strategies.

3.1 Fundamental ideas

Two fundamental ideas of Adaptive Dynamics are that the resident population can be assumed to be in a dynamical equilibrium when new mutants appear, and that the eventual fate of such mutants can be inferred from their initial growth rate when rare in the environment consisting of the resident. This rate is known as the invasion exponent when measured as the initial exponential growth rate of mutants (Diekmann, 2003), and as the basic reproductive number when it measures the expected total number of offspring that a mutant individual will produce in a life time. It can be thought of and is indeed some-

times also referred to as invasion fitness of mutants. To make use of these ideas, a mathematical model is required that explicitly incorporates the traits that are undergoing evolutionary change. The model must describe both the environment and the population dynamics. In many cases, the variable part of the environment consist only of the demography of the current population. Then we now determine the invasion fitness, the initial growth rate of a mutant invading the environment consisting of the resident population. Depending on the model, this can be trivial or very difficult, but once determined the Adaptive Dynamics techniques can be applied independent of the model structure. In the next section we will introduce the basic theory for monomorphic populations.

3.2 Monomorphic population

A population consisting of individuals with the same trait is called monomorphic. We assume that residents are characterised by a quantitative trait x and trait y for mutants, for example, body size, which affects intra-specific competition between individuals. Let $n(x, t)$ be the population density of individuals with character value x at time t . Then their ecological dynamics are given by

$$n'(x, t) = r \times n(x, t) \left(1 - \frac{n_e(x, t)}{k(x)} \right) \quad (3.1)$$

Here, $k(x)$ is the carrying capacity of populations that are monomorphic for trait x . for simplicity, it is assumed that $k(x)$ varies with the trait x and that the intrinsic growth rate r is independent of x . The quantity $n_e(x, t)$ is the effective population density that an individual with character value x experiences at time t .

The effective density is determined by the distribution of phenotypes in the population and by the function $\alpha(x - y)$, which measures the strength of competition exerted by an individual with phenotype y on an individual with phenotyp x . Here, we let $z = x - y$, and we take the function $\alpha(z)$ to be

$$\alpha(z) = \text{Exp} \left[\frac{\sigma^2 \beta^2}{2} \right] \text{Exp} \left[\frac{-(z + \sigma^2 \beta)^2}{2\sigma^2} \right]$$

and represented by [figure 1(a)]. For $\beta = 0$, this function describes symmetric competition; that is, $\alpha(x - y)$ is a symmetric function of the difference $x-y$ with a maximum at 0. This implies that individuals with similar phenotypes compete more strongly with each other than individuals with dissimilar phenotypes, as, for example, when beak size in birds determines the type of seeds eaten.

If $\beta > 0$, $\alpha(x - y)$ describes asymmetric competition, with $\alpha(x - y)$ being maximal for some negative

difference in character values. This implies that larger individuals tend to have a competitive advantage over smaller individuals. In contrast to the asymmetric competition models in Law et al. (1997) and in Kisdi (1999), in which the competitive advantage or disadvantage increased monotonically with phenotypic distance, the function $\alpha(x - y)$ used here implies that competition between very different phenotype is always weak. Such asymmetric competition would, for example, occur when overlaps in resource utilisation between different phenotypes are asymmetric but vanish with increasing phenotypic distance.

For both symmetric and asymmetric competition, the effective density $n_e(x, t)$ is obtained as a weighted sum over all densities $n(x, t)$:

$$n_e(x, t) = \int \alpha(x - y)n(y, t)dy$$

This in fact gives us a Lotka-volterra Model. To determine the invasion fitness $f(x, y)$ of a rare mutant y in a resident population that is monomorphic for the character value x , we assume that mutants invade sufficiently rarely, so that residents are always at (or very close to) their ecological equilibrium $k(x)$ when new mutants appear. Since the mutant is initially rare, its own density is negligible compared to that of the resident, and hence the effective density that the mutant experiences is simply the resident density $k(x)$ weighted by the strength of competition $\alpha(x - y)$ between the mutant and the resident.

Thus, in the initial phase of the invasion when the mutant is rare, the population dynamics of the mutant are given by

$$n'(y, t) = r \times n(y, t) \left(1 - \frac{\alpha(y - x)n(x, t)}{k(y)} \right) \quad (3.2)$$

3.3 Invasion fitness and selection gradient

The invasion fitness of the mutant is its long-term per capita growth rate when rare (Metz et al, 1992; Dieckmann 1994; Rand et al, 1994; Dieckmann & Law 1996; Metz et al, 1996), hence the invasion fitness of the mutant y in the resident x is defined by

$$f(y, x) = r \left(1 - \frac{\alpha(y - x)k(x)}{k(y)} \right) \quad (3.3)$$

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.1: (a) Asexual resource competition, Strength of competition as a function of phenotypic difference between competitors. Symmetric competition is described by the function $\sigma(x - y)$ with $\beta = 0$. An example of asymmetric competition is shown for different values of β . In All cases, σ_α is set to 0.65. (b) Evolutionary dynamics with the asymmetric competition function shown (a). This phenomena is called evolutionary branching. At the branching point, directional selection turns into disruptive selection, which splits the character into two phenotypic clusters.

To determine the evolutionary dynamics, one calculates the derivative of $f(x, y)$ with respect to y and evaluates it at the resident value x . Thus, the crucial quantity is the selection gradient:

$$g(x) = \left. \frac{\partial f(y, x)}{\partial y} \right|_{y=x} \quad (3.4)$$

If $g(x) > 0$, then invasion fitness increases for mutants with higher trait values than the resident, while invasion fitness decreases for mutants with lower trait values. Since $f(x, x) = 0$ by necessity (i.e., the resident neither grows nor declines in its own equilibrium population), this means that mutants with higher trait values can invade, that is, are favoured by natural selection, while mutants with lower trait values are selected against.

Analogous statement in the opposite direction hold for $g(x) < 0$. Thus as, long as $g(x) \neq 0$ selection is directional.

For the evolutionary dynamics, those values x^* are important for which $g(x^*) = 0$. These trait values are called "evolutionary singular" (Metz et al, 1996; Geritz et al, 1998). A singular value x^* is an attractor for the evolutionary dynamics if and only if

$$\left. \frac{dg(x)}{dx} \right|_{x=x^*} < 0$$

for, in the case, $g(x) < 0$ for $x > x^*$ and $g(x) > 0$ for $x < x^*$; hence, lower trait values are favoured when the resident is larger than x^* and higher trait values are favoured when the resident is smaller than the singular value x^* . singular points that are not attractors are of little practical interest since, even starting with resident populations that are very close to such a point, evolution will drive the trait from the singular point.

Two different evolutionary attractors:

If $\left. \frac{\partial^2 f(x, x^*)}{\partial y^2} \right|_{y=x^*} < 0$, the point x^* is a fitness maximum. The evolutionary attractor x^* is, therefore stable against invasion of neighbouring phenotypes, that is, it is an evolutionary stable strategy (ESS), also a "continuously stable strategy" (CSS) (Eshel 1983).

If $\left. \frac{\partial^2 f(x, x^*)}{\partial y^2} \right|_{y=x^*} > 0$, the point x^* is a fitness minimum, and the population therefore experiences disruptive selection. As a consequence, evolutionary branching can occur; that is, the population can

split into two different and diverging phenotypic clusters (Metz et al, 1996; Getz et al, 1997,1998). Metz et al. (1996), Dieckmann and Doebeli (1999), and Kisdi (1999) have shown that evolution toward a fitness minimum, and hence evolutionary branching, is a generic phenomenon in models for resource competition similar to the ones describes above. To complement this theory, we use equation for the function $\alpha(x - y)$ describing the frequency dependence in the competitive interactions, and we take the resource distribution to be of Gaussian form with a maximum at some intermediate phenotype x_0 :

$$k(x) = k_0 \text{Exp} \left[\frac{-(x - x_0)^2}{2\sigma_k^2} \right]. \quad (3.5)$$

We then calculate $g(x)$, equation (3.4), from equations (3.2) and (3.3) , as

$$\begin{aligned} g(x) &= -r \left[\alpha'(0) - \frac{k'(x)}{k(x)} \right] \\ &= -r \left(\frac{x - x_0}{\sigma_k^2} - \beta \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

It follows that $g(x^*) = 0$ for $x^* = x_0 + \beta\sigma_k^2$. Note that the singular point is always larger than the trait value maximizing the carrying capacity. The derivative of $g(x)$ at the singular point x^* is

$$\left. \frac{dg(x)}{dx} \right|_{x=x^*} = -\frac{r}{\sigma_k^2} < 0 \quad (3.7)$$

Hence, x^* always is an evolutionary attractor. In addition, straightforward calculations reveal that condition becomes

$$\left. \frac{\partial^2 f(y, x^*)}{\partial y^2} \right|_{y=x^*} = r \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_\alpha^2} - \frac{1}{\sigma_k^2} \right) > 0 \quad (3.8)$$

This condition is satisfied, and hence x^* is a fitness minimum, if

$$\sigma_\alpha < \sigma_k \quad (3.9)$$

Thus, for a given width α_k of the resource distribution, the singular point x^* is a branching point, that is, an evolutionarily attracting fitness minimum, if the parameter σ_α is small enough. Since σ_α measures the strength of the frequency dependence in the competitive interactions, this implies that, in the model considered, asymmetric competition leads to evolutionary branching whenever the frequency dependence is strong enough. (Note that this result is also true if competition is symmetric; i.e., if $\beta = 0$; see Dieckmann and Doebeli 1999). An example of the corresponding evolutionary dynamics is shown in figure 1B. (This figure is based on an individual-based model) Starting with small phenotypic values, the evolutionary dynamics show a steady increase in the trait value until the system reaches the branching point. Because larger phenotypes have an intrinsic advantage, branching occurs at a

phenotypic value that is larger than the value that maximizes the carrying capacity. After branching, the phenotype in one branch continues to increase, while in the other branch it decreases again. Note that the population size is different in the two branches, with the branch that consists of larger individuals and is located farther away from the optimal carrying capacity having fewer individuals. For a more thorough treatment and additional examples of evolutionary branching under symmetric and asymmetric competition, (see Dieckmann and Doebeli (1999) and Kisdi(1999)). The adaptive dynamics outlined here are for a monomorphic population, where by only one trait is evolving. In the next section we outline the adaptive dynamics of a dimorphic population (predator-prey community) where by we focus on two evolving traits.

4. The predator-prey community

Predator and prey evolve together. The prey is part of the predator's environment, and the predator dies if it does not get food, so it evolves whatever is necessary in order to consume the prey: speed, stealth, camouflage (to hide while approaching the prey), a good sense of smell, sight, or hearing (to find the prey), immunity to the prey's poison, poison (to kill the prey) the right kind of mouth parts or digestive system, etc. Likewise, the predator is part of the prey's environment, and the prey dies if it is eaten by the predator, so it evolves whatever is necessary to avoid being eaten: speed, camouflage (to hide from the predator), a good sense of smell, sight, or hearing (to detect the predator), thorns, poison (to spray when approached or bitten), etc.

Models of phenotypic evolution are described by ecological processes describing the dynamics of predator and prey populations (in this context). This ensures that the process of natural selection directing evolution is driven explicitly by the ecology of predator-prey interactions. For simplicity we focus on a single phenotypic trait in each species; in view of the importance of body size in determining interactions between predator and prey (Cohen et al, 1993), one might think of these traits as body sizes, s_1 and s_2 , of predator and prey, respectively.

Now we describe the population dynamics in our community, hence it is necessary to define those ecological processes that affect the population sizes of the two evolving species (table 1). Table 1(a) clearly describes the birth and death events that are dependent on phenotype, these being the events that arise from encounters with other individuals in the population, This is opposed to the constant birth and death events given in Table 1(b).

Evolutionary processes in the community require a mechanism for generating phenotypic variation (changes of the genes of a particular species) on which natural selection caused by the interaction between predator and prey can operate. We will assume that variation is caused by a simple mutation process; we assume that the genetic systems of the species are clonal. Table 1(c) shows that each birth event gives rise with probabilities μ_1 and μ_2 to a mutant offspring in the phenotypic traits s_1 and s_2 of prey and predator, respectively. The new phenotypes are chosen according to the mutation distributions, M_1 and M_2 of prey and predator, respectively.

Natural selection arises from the dependence of the birth and death probabilities per unit time α , β and γ on the phenotypes of the interacting individuals. We use functions as described in Figure 4.1. Thus the function α , which characterizes the ecological processes responsible for self-limitation in the prey's

population size, is taken to be parabolic such that intermediate phenotypes are favoured in the absence of the predator [figure. 4.1(a)]. The function β describes the effect of a predator on the probability of death of the prey is taken to be bivariate Gaussian [figure. 4.1(b)], on the grounds that the predator is likely to show some degree of specialization in the size of prey it chooses relative to its own size (Cohen et al, 1993). On the basis that what is bad for the prey is good for the predator, the function γ is related to β by a constant of proportionality, $\gamma = h\beta$. We call h the harvesting efficiency.

Table 1. definition of birth, death and mutation processes for a prey individual of size s_1 and predator of size s_2 .

(a) Birth and death processes affected by phenotype.

Target individual	Encountered individual	Birth/death event	Probability of event per encounter per unit time
1. prey s_1	prey \hat{s}_1	death of prey s_1	$\alpha(s_1, s_2)$ *
2. prey s_1	predator s_2	death of prey s_1	$\beta(s_1, s_2)$
3. predator s_2	prey s_1	birth of predator s_2	$\gamma(s_1, s_2)$

(b) Birth and death processes independent of phenotype

Target individual	Birth/death event	Probability of event per encounter per unit time
1. prey s_1	birth of prey s_1	r_1
2. predator s_2	death of predator s_2	r_2

(c) Mutation processes

Birth event	Mutation event	Probability distribution **
birth of prey s_1	prey $s_1 \rightarrow s'_1$	$(1 - \mu_1)\delta(s'_1 - s_1) + \mu_1 M_1(s'_1 - s_1)$
birth of predator s_2	predator $s_2 \rightarrow s'_2$	$(1 - \mu_2)\delta(s'_2 - s_2) + \mu_2 M_2(s'_2 - s_2)$

* This death event is taken to be dependent only on the phenotype s_1 of the target individual, not on that of the

encountered individual \hat{s}_1 .

$\star \star \mu_i$ is the probability that the birth event in species i is a mutant; δ is the Dirac δ function; M_1 is the distribution.

The ecological community here extends the model of (Marrow et al, 1992) and it provides a full dynamical description of the birth, death and mutation processes. It generalizes the former account in the sense that (i) it allows stochastic population dynamics arising from individual-based encounters, and (ii) it permits the populations to have polymorphic phenotypic distributions since multiple phenotypic trait values may be present simultaneously in each species. From Table 1, a special case the well-known Lotka-Volterra equations is recovered.

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{n}_1 &= n_1(r_1 - \alpha(s_1)n_1 - \beta(s_1, s_2)n_2) \\ \dot{n}_2 &= n_2(-r_2 + \gamma(s_1, s_2)n_1) \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

for the population sizes, n_1 and n_2 , of prey and predator, respectively, by assuming no mutations, random encounters, deterministic population dynamics (the population sizes of the species are large), and monomorphic phenotypic distributions (only one phenotype present within each species).

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.1: Specification of the coevolutionary community given in Table 1. The functions used to describe the effect of phenotype (s_1, s_2) on the birth and death probabilities arising from encounters between individuals are: (a) prey self-limitation $\alpha(s_1)/u = c_1 - c_1 s_1 + c_3 s_1^2$, (b) effect of predator on prey $\beta(s_1, s_2)/u = \exp(-\delta_1^2 + 2c_4 \delta_1 \delta_2 - \delta_2^2)$, where $\delta_1 = (s_1 - c_5)/c_6$ and $\delta_2 = (s_2 - c_7)/c_8$, and u is a constant that scales population sizes. Parameters take values: $c_1 = 3.0, c_2 = 10.0, c_3 = 10.0, c_4 = 0.6, c_5 = 0.5, c_6 = 0.22, c_7 = 0.5, c_8 = 0.25$. The function $\gamma(s_1, s_2)$ is not shown since it is related to $\beta(s_1, s_2)$ by the constant of proportionality h . The constant birth and death terms are: $r_1 = 0.5, r = 0.05$. Mutation parameters used in the paper are $\mu_1 = 10^{-3}, \mu_2 = 10^{-3}$; M_1 and M_2 are normal distributions with mean 0 and $\sqrt{\text{var}M_1} = 2 \times 10^{-3}$ and $\sqrt{\text{var}M_2} = 2 \times 10^{-3}$, except where otherwise stated. The quantity $u = 10^{-3}$ is constant throughout.

5. Dynamical Model Of Coevolution

Equations (4.1) illustrate how the general coevolutionary process defined in Table 1 can be reduced by making appropriate simplifying assumptions. In a similar spirit, a dynamical model for the change in phenotypic traits s_1 and s_2 of the prey and predator respectively will be shown in this section.

Monomorphic deterministic model

This is a deterministic approximation to the monomorphic stochastic model above (see Dieckman et al., (1995)). It is given in terms of a system of ordinary differential equations describing the expected evolutionary paths in the phenotype space. The monomorphic deterministic model is given by the equation:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \langle s \rangle = \left(\frac{1}{2} \mu_i \text{var} M_i \right) n_i(\langle s \rangle) \frac{\partial}{\partial s'_i} f_i(s'_i, \langle s \rangle) \Big|_{s'_i = \langle s_i \rangle} \quad (5.1)$$

(i) The term $\left(\frac{1}{2} \mu_i \text{var} M_i \right) n_i(\langle s \rangle)$ captures the influence of mutation on the coevolutionary dynamics. The factor $\frac{1}{2} \mu_i \text{var} M_i$, called the evolutionary rate constant, is affected by the proportion μ_i of births that produce mutants and by the variance $\text{var} M_i$ of the mutation distribution in the trait s_i . Together with the population size n_i , all these terms are non-negative, so term as a whole serves to scale the rate of evolutionary change.

(ii) The term $f_i(s'_i, \langle s \rangle) \Big|_{s'_i = \langle s_i \rangle}$ measures the impact of selection as it determines the direction of the evolutionary change. when the derivative of f_i is positive (respectively negative), mutants with increased (respectively decreased) phenotypic values s_i will be advantageous in the environment given by $\langle s \rangle$. The lines on which this term is zero are isolines of the monomorphic deterministic dynamics.

Note that the fitness of the mutants is given by, $f(s'_i, s) = b_i(s'_i, s) - d_i(s'_i, s)$, which denote the per capita birth, death and growth probabilities per unit time of phenotype s'_i in an environment given by the phenotype s . For the predator-prey community we take, $b_1(s'_1, s) = r_1$, $d_1(s'_1, s) = \alpha(s'_1)n_1(s) + \beta(s'_1, s_2)n_2(s)$, $b_2(s'_2, s) = \gamma(s_1, s'_2)n_1(s)$, and $d_2(s'_2, s) = r_2$. The model defined here is used to produce the results in the next section.

6. Results

In this section we describe the variety of possible evolutionary outcomes in a predator-prey community, using the monomorphic deterministic model. In the case of the monomorphic phenotypic dynamics, we can immediately infer from eqns (4.1) that there is a region in the phenotype space where both species can coexist with positive population densities. Only within this region can the predator population harvest the prey sufficiently to survive; given a pair of phenotypes (s_1, s_2) outside this region, the predator population is driven to extinction by the population dynamics. Accordingly, coevolution of the predator and prey can only be observed within this region of coexistence. For a coevolving predator-prey community starting with phenotypes in the region of coexistence, there are eventually three possible outcomes.

1. Evolution to a fixed point. In Fig 6.1(a) the phenotypic values tend to an equilibrium point; once this is reached, no further evolution occurs. There are in fact three fixed points at the intersection of the isoclines (i.e $\dot{s}_1 = 0, \dot{s}_2 = 0$) in this example, as can be seen from the accompanying phase portrait [fig. 6.1(b)]; two of these are attractors and they are separated by the stable manifold of the third which is a saddle point. Notice that the coevolutionary process here is multistable with two attractors having disjunct domains of attraction; thus there may be no more reason for a particular observed asymptotic evolutionary state than the more or less arbitrary initial conditions.
2. Evolution to extinction. In Fig.6.3(a) the co-evolutionary process drives the phenotypic values towards the boundary of the region of coexistence[see fig.3(b)]. There the predator population goes extinct and the predator phenotype is no longer defined. The phenotype space of the community collapses from (s_1, s_2) to the one dimensional space s_1 where the prey phenotype continues to evolve to its own equilibrium point. Note here that the extinction of the predator is driven by the evolutionary dynamics in (s_1, s_2) and not merely by the population dynamics in (n_1, n_2) ,
3. Evolutionary cycling. In Fig. 6.2(a) the coevolutionary process in the predator-prey community continues indefinitely mutants replace residents in a cyclic manner such that the phenotypes eventually return to their original values and do not reach an equilibrium point. As can be seen from Fig.6.3(b), the attractor is a limit cycle, confirming the conjecture made by Marrow et al. (1992) that Red Queen coevolution can occur in this predator-prey community.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6.1: this figure shows the patterns of evolution of prey and predator phenotypes obtained from the monomorphic deterministic mode. (a) the solution tends to an equilibrium point over the course of time, it is obtained using parameter values in figure 4.1 with $h=1$. (b) shows the phase portrait of the phenotype from which (a) is drawn, equilibrium points occur at the intersection of the isoclines. parameter values used here are the same as used in figure 5.1

(a)

(b)

Figure 6.2: Example of evolutionary using the monomorphic deterministic model in (a) and (b). Graph (a) shows the values of the prey (s_1) and predator (s_2) phenotypes as functions of time. The corresponding orbits are shown as continuous lines in the phase spaces given in graph (b). parameter values for these simulations are identical and are set as in figure 4.1, expect $\mu_1 = 10^{-2}$, $\mu_2 = 10^{-2}$ and with $h=0.14$.

Figure 6.3: (a) solution for community that evolves to predator extinction with time, after this time the prey population continues to evolve in the absence of the prey. Parameter values as in figure 4.1, except $c_1 = 1.0, c_2 = 1.0$ and with $h=1$. (b) Phase portrait of the phenotype space from which (c) is drawn.

7. Discussion

The result of this analysis is limit cycles, in which the predator and prey phenotypes continue to change indefinitely, are a natural outcome in a coevolutionary community and are common in many aspects of nature.

The classification of the outcomes of phenotypic evolution can be constructed from two dichotomies. The first depends on whether an attractor exists, and the second on whether the attractor is a fixed point. This gives three classes of dynamics.

(i) evolution to a fixed-point attractor with stationary phenotypes, (ii) evolution to an attractor that is not a fixed point on which the phenotypes continue to change indefinitely, and (iii) evolution without an attractor, such that the phenotypes take more and more extreme values (evolutionary limit cycles).

We can from the definition of the Red queen in the introduction, Red Queen dynamics would encompass classes (ii) and (iii). Class (iii) is unrealistic for most kinds of phenotypes and, if the Red Queen were to depend on the existence of such dynamics in nature, one could reasonably conclude that Red Queen dynamics would be very unusual (Dieckmann et al., (1995)) But this would be to miss class (ii), and dynamics of this kind we have shown here to be feasible. Hence we can say the limit cycle is but one of a number of non-equilibrium attractors; for instance in systems with more than two coevolving species, chaotic evolutionary attractors could be found. Cyclic phenotype dynamics can occur in coevolution as is well known from theoretical studies of genetic polymorphisms under frequency-dependent selection (e.g Akin, 1987; Seger, 1992), and research into the dynamics of strategy frequencies (e.g Nowak & Sigmund, 1989). The system considered here is different in two respects. First, the trait values are continuous, whereas cyclic dynamics have typically been observed in polymorphic systems with large qualitative differences between a small number of coexisting phenotypes. Second, and more important, the underlying genetic process here would be a sequence of gene substitutions in which mutants keep replacing the resident types rather than one in which the genes always coexist and undergo oscillations in frequency. Thus we are here looking at a process operating on an altogether larger evolutionary scale. The monomorphic deterministic dynamic described here in fact turns out to be canonical (Dieckmann & Law, 1995), and can be derived from other starting points such as quantitative genetics (Abrams et al., 1993). It seems, therefore, that there is a large class of models of phenotypic coevolution with the potential for non-equilibrium asymptotic states. This needs to be emphasized because the assumption

that asymptotic states of evolution are fixed points underlies much contemporary evolutionary thought. This assumption and the techniques that go with it (in particular evolutionarily stable strategies) are clearly not appropriate for dealing with non-equilibrium asymptotic states. The prevailing view among evolutionary biologists, centred on equilibrium points, needs to be extended to a dynamical framework to assimilate the Red Queen.

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